

Original Article

PROMOTING ENTREPRENEURIAL MIND-SET OF UNIVERSITY BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS FOR CAPACITY BUILDING IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The study determined Business Educators' opinions on promoting entrepreneurial mindset of Business Education students for capacity Building in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. The population comprised 30 Business Educators from two government owned universities (UNN and ESUT). The instrument was a-20 item structured questionnaire (PEMOBESQ) developed by the researchers. The instrument was duly validated by three experts. The reliability was done using Cronbach Alpha which yielded coefficient of 0.68, indicating that the instrument is reliable. The two research questions were answered using mean with standard deviation. While the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test. Results of data analysis relating to the study have shown that, Business Educators strategies promote entrepreneurial mindset of Business Education students for capacity Building in Enugu State. The findings also showed, Institutional related strategies promote entrepreneurial mindset of Business Education students for capacity Building in Enugu State. The hypotheses tested showed that, there was no significant difference in the mean scores of Educators in Federal universities and their counterparts in the State on Business Educators and institutional related strategies respectively for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education for capacity building in Enugu state. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Business students should be exposed to the needed entrepreneurial skills. Again, Institutions where Business Education is offered should employ more lecturers with bias in Entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial skills, University Business Education students, Capacity Building and strategies.

Introduction

The role of Entrepreneurship in driving economic growth and development has become increasingly recognized globally. In Nigeria particularly in Enugu State Entrepreneurship is seen as a vital tool for addressing pressing issues such as unemployment, poverty and underdevelopment. Entrepreneurship is

one of the options of Business Education in universities (Core Curriculum) and Minimum Academic standards (CCMAS, 2023). Entrepreneurship Education particularly in university is an answer to the ever increasing unemployment problem in our society. According to Enebe (2018), Entrepreneurship Education is a special training

given to students to help them acquire the skills, ideas and managerial abilities and capabilities for self-employment rather than being employed for payment. Moreso, Entrepreneurship Education is the process of teaching and learning the knowledge, skills and mindset vital to start, grow and manage a successful entrepreneurial venture.

According to Ubogu (2020) Entrepreneurship Education is aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial mindset, which involves innovation, value creation, risk taking and resourcefulness. In order word, entrepreneurial mindset include risk taking, adaptability and resilience.

In the words of Dweck (2020), mindset influences how one link, feel and behave in any given section. Mindset is a set of beliefs that shape how one make sense of the world and oneself. Mindset believes that one's talents and abilities can be developed over time through effort and persistence. Moreso Fixed mindset assumes that abilities and intelligence are fixed traits that cannot be changed. Hence, the need to get University Business Education students smarter and more talented by improving their entrepreneurial mindset.

Entrepreneurial mindset is a way of one's thinking and behaving that enable individuals to identify opportunities, take calculated risks, and create value through innovation and Entrepreneurship. Menipaz (2021) opined that, entrepreneurial mindset include but not limited to curiosity, commitment, optimism, flexibility, ownership, leadership connection, self-respect, independence drive, focus and determination. University Business Education students with an entrepreneurial mindset should often be curious creative and resourceful (Ugwunwoti 2025). Entrepreneurial mindset should be seen as a constant need by university Business Education students to improve their skills, learn from mistakes and take continuous action idea. For university Business Education students to, improve their entrepreneurial mindset they must acquire needed Entrepreneurial skills.

Entrepreneurial skills are the abilities required to successfully start, manage and grow a business. It can technical, soft and essential skills. Akele (2021), opined that Entrepreneurial skills are the abilities of individual to exploit an idea and create an enterprise not only for personal gain but also for social and developmental gain. Moreover, Udo-Aka (2020) suggested that, Entrepreneurial skills when acquired helps the youth to have skills associated with entrepreneurship, such as the ability to take initiative, creatively seek out and identify business opportunities; develop budgets and forecast resources needs, understand various options for acquiring capital and the trade-offs associated with each option, communicate effectively and make market oneself and one's idea. Moreover, for university business students, it is one thing to have these skills and another is to get the entrepreneurial mindset to be promoted among them for capacity building.

Capacity building is the process of developing and strengthening the skills, knowledge and abilities of individuals, organizations or communities to improve their performance and achieve their goals. Akinola (2017) sees the principal intention of capacity building as equipping people with knowledge to qualify them for a particular position, improve skills and enhance efficiency.

In Business Education, capacity building is refers to as the process of developing and enhancing the skills, knowledge and attitudes of individuals to improve their performance and effectiveness in business settings. When entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education students is promoted, the capacity building is also assured.

University Business Education students are individuals pursuing higher education in business related fields such as Accounting, Office Technology and Management, Entrepreneurship and marketing. Oduma (2021) opined that, Business Education students are the group beneficiaries of Business Education idea. Moreover, the University Business

Education students can improve their entrepreneurial mindset through needed strategies.

Strategies are long-term plans of action designed to achieve specific goals or objectives. Strategies refers to deliberate plans and approach to achieve specific learning objectives, enhance students engagement, and develop essential skills for future business professionals. (Ugwunwoti, Eya and Aruah, 2024).

To promote entrepreneurial mindset of these students for capacity building, Business Educators related strategies and institutional related strategies are needed. According to Afolayan (2013), Business Educators related strategies are the methods, approaches and techniques used by Educators to impart knowledge, develop skills, promote attitudes and support student access. Going by this definition, Business Educators are strong stakeholders in improving Entrepreneurial mindset of her students.

Another strategy needed for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of University Business Education students is institutional related strategies. Institutional strategies are the policies, practices, and initiatives implemented by educational institutions to create an entrepreneurial development and prepare them for success. Chibuike (2013), noted that, if institutions that have the Business Education program must achieve their goals, they must put in place quality enhancing strategies that will ensure the production of quality graduates for national development program in tertiary institutions. University Business Education students are expected to develop knowledge, skills and attitudes to promote entrepreneurial mindset for capacity building. Imparting these competencies is the sole concern of Business Educators.

Business Educators is the implementer of the Business Education programme. . According to Nsude (2015), the teacher (a Business Educator) is the main force and the last person that ensure that any programme is implemented according to specification, he decides to teach and at what time. A Business Educator according to Chibuike (2019) is a

person who understands the vocational interest of his students and the significance values of business concepts which contributes to the development of economically and vocationally able members of the society. Business Educators are expected to improve the entrepreneurial mindset of their students while in the classrooms for capacity Building. The Business Educators in this context are those teaching in Universities.

A university is an institution of higher Education and research that grants academic degree in various field of study (Ugwunwoti, Eya and Aruah, 2024). Moreover, Ajolayan (2013) opined that a university is an institution that combines teaching, research and service to society, producing graduates equipped with skills, knowledge and value for the global market. Any organized university is responsible for teaching, researching and community service. In Enugu State, there are both Federal and State owned universities offering Business Education Programme. Ugwunwoti and Agbo (2022) opined that State universities are owned, financed and controlled by government and vice versa Federal Universities.

Despite the number of Business Educators and universities offering Business Education Programmes, the entrepreneurial mindset of their students for capacity building seems to be lacking. Even when they tend to know about, it is theory based not practical's as observed by the researchers. This becomes an issue that bordered the researchers to asses on Promoting Entrepreneurial Mindset of University Business Education students for capacity building in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

University Business Education students are individuals pursuing higher Education in business related fields at university. These students are typically enrolled in undergraduate or post graduate programmes, studying, Accounting, office Technology and Management, Marketing and Entrepreneurship. The primary aim of

Entrepreneurship is to equip them with the needed skills for sustainability.

Despite the growing need for entrepreneurship Business Education students in Enugu State students seem to be lacking necessary skills and mindset to start and sustain successful business. Records have it, that Business Education students in Universities in Enugu State are facing challenges in translating theoretical knowledge into practical entrepreneurial skills hindering their abilities to contribute to the state's economic development.

It is against this background that, this work on Promoting Entrepreneurial Mindset of University, Business Education Students for Capacity Building in Enugu State was carried out.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was on the Promoting Entrepreneurial Mindset of University Business Education Students for Capacity Building in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine Business Educators related strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education students for capacity building in Enugu State.
2. Ascertain institutional related strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of University Business Education students for capacity building in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the Business Educators strategies for Promoting entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State?
2. What are the institutional related strategies for Promoting entrepreneurial mindset among university Business Education students for capacity building in Enugu State?

Hypothesis

The under listed hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively on Business Educators related strategies for Promoting Entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on institutional related strategies for Promoting Entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was employed in the study. According to Nworgu (2015), descriptive survey is the one in which a group of people is studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people considered to be representative of the entire group. The study was carried out in two government owned universities in Enugu State. (University of Nigeria, Nsukka and Enugu state university of Science and Technology). The population for the study comprised of 24 Business Educators from university of Nigeria, Nsukka, and 6 from Enugu State University of Science and Technology respectively totaling 30 Business Educators. The was census sampling because the population size was manageable.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers entitled: Promoting Entrepreneurial Mindset of Business Education Student's Questionnaire (PEMOBESQ). The instrument has three sections. Section A was on bio-data. Section B on Business Educators strategies and section C on Institutional-related strategies. The rating responses were Strongly Agree (SA); Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with numerical values of 4,3,2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts. Two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education (Measurement and

Evaluation) all from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu state. To test the reliability of the instrument, 20 Business Educators in universities in Anambra state were used. Cronbach Alpha estimate was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, which yielded a coefficient index 0.67. This index indicated that, the instrument is reliable enough to be used for the study.

The researchers with the help of three research assistants used direct delivery techniques in the administration of the instrument to the respondents. At the end of the administration of the instrument, all the 30 copies were returned and used for the study; representing 100% rate of return. Mean and standard deviation was used in answering the research questions; while t-test was used in testing the null

hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at the appropriate degree of freedom.

Decision rule for answering the research questions was based on the real limits of the mean thus:

Strongly Agree	3.50 - 4.00
Agree	2.50 - 3.49
Disagree	1.50 - 2.49
Strongly disagree	1.00 - 1.49

For the hypotheses, when the calculate t-value was equal to or greater than the table value, the null hypotheses was rejected, otherwise it was rejected.

Results

Research Questions 1

What are the Business Educators related strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of universities business Education students for capacity building in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean Scores and standard deviation of Business Educators in Business Educators Strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of University Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State.

S/N	Items on	Federal n = 24		State n= 6		Overall n =30		Decisio n
	Business Educators related strategies to:	\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	SD ₂	\bar{x}_2	\bar{x}	SD	
1	Incorporate real-wide projects	3.25	0.84	3.05	0.86	3.15	0.85	Agree
2	Pair students with Develop creative solutions to successful complex problems	3.16	1.02	3.02	0.79	3.09	0.905	Agree
3	Articulate ideas	3.12	0.86	2.92	0.82	3.02	0.84	Agree
4	Take calculated risks to achieve business goals	2.81	0.89	2.86	1.03	2.84	0.96	Agree
5	Develop novel solutions	2.96	0.99	2.94	1.04	2.95	1.015	Agree
6	Mange business effectively	3.00	1.10	3.07	0.92	3.04	1.01	Agree
7	Manage time effectively	2.84	0.88	2.22	0.96	2.53	0.92	Agree
8	Adjust to changing circumstances	2.36	0.88	2.36	0.99	2.31	0.935	Agree
9	Build networks in business	3.23	0.82	3.04	0.84	3.34	0.83	Agree
10	Manage resources	3.13	1.03	3.24	1.02	3.09	1.025	agree
	Cluster mean/SD	2.09	0.93	2.86	0.93	2.93	0.93	Agree

Table 1 shows that items 1 to 10 with mean scores of 3.15, 3.09, 3.02, 2.84, 2.95, 3.04, 2.53, 3.24 and 3.09 respectively. This means that, the itemized Business Educators strategies can promote entrepreneurial mindset of University Business Education students for capacity building in Enugu State. The grand mean value of 2.93 also attested to that; while cluster

standard deviation of 0.93 shows homogeneity of opinions of the respondents.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the Mean scores of Business Educators in Federal Universities and

their other counterparts in State on Business Educators Strategies for Promoting entrepreneurial

mindset of University Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State.

Table 2: Summary Table of t-test analysis of the mean scores of Business Educators on Business Educators strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset for capacity building in Enugu State

Status	NO	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-table	t-cal	
Federal	24	2.99	0.93	28	1.96	0.48	Not significant
State	06	2.86	0.93				

Table 2 shows that the calculated t- value at 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom is 0.48, while the table value or critical value under the same conditions is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the critical or table value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant. This invariably means that, there is no significant difference between the Mean Scores of Business Educators in Federal Universities and their

counterparts in the State type on Business Educators Strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of University Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State.

Research Questions 2: What are the Institutional strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of Education students for capacity building in Enugu State?

Table 3. Mean Scores and standard deviation of Business Educators on Institutional strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State.

S/N	Items on	Federal n = 24		State n= 6		Overall n =30		Decisio n
	business educators related strategies to:	\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	SD ₂	\bar{x}_2	\bar{x}	SD	
11	Incorporate real-world projects	2.81	0.96	2.24	0.98	2.53	0.97	Agree
12	Pair students with successful entrepreneurs for guidance	2.90	0.99	2.60	0.92	2.75	0.955	Agree
13	Invite entrepreneurs to share their experiences	1.76	0.94	2.39	0.97	2.08	0.955	Agree
14	Establish or partner with incubators to provide supports for student startups	1.46	0.75	1.45	0.88	1.46	0.815	Agree
15	Organize events, conferences to connect students with professionals	2.06	1.01	2.01	1.04	2.04	1.025	Agree
16	Incorporate courses focused on entrepreneurial thinking	1.44	0.80	1.27	0.69	1.36	0.705	Agree
17	Encourage students to develop business plans	1.47	0.84	1.23	0.63	1.35	0.755	Agree
18	Support student led-club focused on entrepreneurship	1.38	0.61	1.25	0.68	1.32	0.645	Agree

19	Partner with local businesses	1.40	0.83	1.27	0.59	1.34	0.71	Agree
20	Encourage students to solve real world-problems through entrepreneurial projects	1.46	0.88	1.37	0.82	1.42	0.85	Agree
	Cluster Mean/SD	1.81	1.71	0.88	0.82	1.8	0.84	Agree

Results data in table 3 above, reveals that items 11 to 20 with scores of 2.53, 2.75, 2.08, 1.46, 2.04, 1.36, 1.35, 1.32, 1.34 and 1.42 respectively as agreed by the respondents. The grand mean value of 1.76 also attested to that; while cluster standard deviation of 0.82 shows homogeneity of opinions of respondents.

Table 4: Summary Table of t-test analysis of mean score of Business Educators in Federal and state Universities on Instructional related strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education students for capacity building in Enugu

Status	NO	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-table	t-cal	
Federal	24	1.81	0.88	28	1.96	0.38	Not significant
State	06	1.71	0.82				

Table 4 shows that, the calculated t-values of 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom is 0.38, the table value or critical value under the same conditions is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the critical value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant. This means that, there is no significant difference in the Mean Scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on Institutional related Strategies for Promoting Entrepreneurial mindset of University Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

The data presented in Table 1, shows that Business Educators in Federal and State in Enugu State were in agreement that itemized Business Educators related strategies. These strategies are: incorporate real-world projects to develop entrepreneurial skills, pair students with successful entrepreneurs for guidance, invite entrepreneurs to share the experience among others. The findings is in-line

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities respectively on institutional related strategies for promoting University Business Education students for capacity building in Enugu state.

with Afolayan (2013) that Business Educators impact knowledge, develop skills, promote attitude and support students access. The null hypothesis one tested on the Business Educators related strategies showed that, there was no significant difference between the Mean Scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on Business Educators related strategies for Promoting entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of universities had no significant influence in their opinions.

Data obtained regarding research question two, revealed that Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in Enugu State were in agreement that, Institutional related strategies can promote entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State. These strategies are: encourage students to develop solutions to real-world business problems,

assign projects that require students to develop plan, use business simulations to teach entrepreneurial concepts, invite entrepreneurs to share their experiences among others. The findings is in harmony with Chibuikwe (2013) that if institution that have the Business Education Programme must achieve their goals, such institution must put in place quality enhancing strategies that will ensure the production of quality graduates for National development. The null hypothesis two tested, showed that Business Educators in Federal Universities and their counterparts in State type did not differ significantly in their Mean Scores on Institutional related Strategies for promoting entrepreneurial mindset of university Business Education Students for capacity building in Enugu State. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of universities had no significant influence in their opinions.

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Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that university Business Education students' entrepreneurial mindset can be promoted through itemized Business Educators and instructional related strategies respectively for capacity building in Enugu State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that:

1. Entrepreneurship Education should be integrated into Business Education curricular.
2. University Business Education Students should be exposed to the needed entrepreneurial skills.
3. Authorities concern should employ more Business Educators with bias in Entrepreneurship Education.

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